

DISCOURSE OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN LINGUISTIC ASPECTS

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Abstract. The article examines the problem of tourism discourse as an object of integral linguistics. The main goal of the work is the theoretical justification for the use of an integral approach to the study of tourism discourse, the definition of the concept of tourism discourse as an integral dispersed object and the creation of its integral meta-model.

Keywords: integral approach, integral model, tourism discourse, dispersed object, sector.

INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization and growing intercultural contacts, more and more attention is being paid to the development of the tourism industry. These issues are of particular importance in linguistics, where the problem of tourism discourse does not have a holistic interpretation, since it was studied fragmentarily, within the framework of various paradigms of scientific knowledge, as a rule, using the material of a single language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main goal of the study is to develop the theoretical foundations of an integral approach to solving the problem of tourism discourse: substantiating the concept of tourism discourse as an integral dispersed object and creating its integral meta-model.

Tourism discourse has become the object of close linguistic research since the beginning of the 21st century. Research is carried out within the framework of various approaches: linguostylistic (E.N. Vaganova, K.A. Egorova, T.A. Khromova, etc.), linguopragmatic (A.A. Mikityuk, L.P. Tarnaeva, N. .V. Filatov and others), linguocultural (E.V. Zayukova, E.Yu. Novikova, M.V. Povarnitsyn, etc.), linguocognitive (T.B. Nikiforova, N.A. Tyuleneva, E.M. Shevchenko and others), psycholinguistic (O.A. Kuzina, E.V. Tretyakova, etc.), linguodidactic (N.D. Mashlykina, R.B. Ruzhentseva, etc.) and others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are different points of view on the issue of determining the typological status of tourism discourse. So, N.V. Filatova defines tourism discourse as speech activity on the topic "travel" and the corresponding set of texts, as a special type of institutional discourse, advertising, which is

distinguished on the basis of the following criteria: specific localization of the communicative event, special composition participants, the presence of their characteristic goals and strategies, a special key concept (journey), specific content of speech, the existence of characteristic mental procedures, codes and subcodes [2, 3].

Integral linguistics allows us to consider any linguistic object as an integral set of interdependent and interdependent units of four sectors: cognitive, linguistic, cultural and social, actualized in the process of communicative activity [4].

From this perspective, tourism discourse is an integral, dispersed phenomenon, a process of combining communicative activities of representatives of different societies, during which fragments of knowledge, language, national culture and social space associated with a certain locus are verbalized in their global unity and interdependence and control of non-speech activities of communicants takes place [4].

In the *cognitive* sector, tourism discourse is a fragment of knowledge of a certain subject area. Declarative knowledge of tourism discourse in a broad sense is knowledge of the subject area “travel”, which consists of individual concepts combined into topics, thematic sections and areas depending on the type of tourism. Procedural knowledge finds its expression in the form of a macrostructure of discourse, which is determined by its pistemic situation, for example, “problem - solution”, “general - particular”, “particular - general”, etc.

In the *social* sector, tourism discourse is a fragment of social space, a social situation structured using special rules of social behavior, behind which there is extra-verbal activity. The units of the social sector are social concepts, such as participants in communication (tourists and tourism workers), as well as typical social structures of communication, such as genre and style.

In the *cultural* sector, tourism discourse represents fragments of the culture of the people and country where the trip is taking place, and the culture of the country where tourists come from. These fragments may or may not coincide. The cultural sector is based on the cultural values of the people, their attitude to nature, time, space, power, communication, etc.

In the *linguistic* sector, tourism discourse is a fragment of language in which knowledge, cultural values, social actions and communicative attitudes are represented using linguistic means and categories. The main representative of tourist discourse is the tourist text as a subject-sign model of discourse, the units of which are updated in the process of communication.

The *communicative* component of tourism discourse is a set of communicative goals and strategies that are determined by the type of tourism discourse, for example, in addition to the informational purpose, it is educational and aesthetic for the discourse of intellectual tourism, health-improving for medical tourism, educational – for educational tourism, etc. Of particular interest is the study of the correlation of communicative strategies of tourism discourse with units of all four of its sectors.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the integral approach allowed us to consider tourism discourse as an integral, dispersed phenomenon, a process of combining communicative activities of representatives of different societies, during which fragments of knowledge, language, national culture and social space associated with a certain locus are verbalized, in their global unity and interdependence, the non-speech activities of communicants are controlled. Developing a typology of tourism discourse, filling the integral metamodel with specific content depending on the type of tourism discourse, as well as simultaneous tracking of the correlation of units of all sectors of the integral model are promising areas of integral research.

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